

Analysis of Polymer-Filler Interaction in Filled Polyethylene

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ABSTRACT

An analytical study was made of the structure, thickness and properties of the interphase in Aerosil-filled high-density polyethylene. The interphase of the composites was isolated by extraction of the non-adsorbed polymer with solvent (xylene) and by subjecting the filler particles to a dissolving procedure with hydrofluoric acid.

Molecular mass distributions of the HDPE-fractions were determined by GPC (Gel Permeation Chromatography) and compared with Meissner's theory. An advanced differential scanning calorimetric method allowed us to measure the heat of fusion, melting temperature and crystallization temperature of the polymer fractions. The analysis included dynamic-mechanical experiments and theoretical considerations which gave insight into the influence of specific mechanical interphase properties on the storage shear modulus G' , the loss modulus G'' and $\tan \delta$ of the composites.

NOMENCLATURE

BP	Bound polymer, the volume fraction of polymer adsorbed and insolubilized by the filler.
U	Unbound polymer, $U = 1 - BP$
ΔR	Average thickness of bound polymer layer.
ρ_f	Density of filler in kg/m^3 .
A_f	Specific surface of filler in m^2/kg .
y	Number of structural units in a polymer chain.
$w(y)dy$	The weight fraction of polymer having values of y between y and y + dy.
$w_u(y)dy$	The weight fraction of unbound polymer having values of y between y and y + dy.
$w_{BP}(y)dy$	The weight fraction of bound polymer having values of y between y and y + dy.
$q = \frac{M_0 c A_f}{A_0 N_a}$	Fraction of adsorbed structural units.
M_0	Molecular weight of structural unit.
c	Filler concentration in g/g of polymer.

A_0	Surface area of filler per single reactive site.
N_A	Avagadro number $N_A = 6.023 \times 10^{23}$.
$\Delta H_{BP} + \text{Aerosil}$	Heat of fusion in J/g of bound polymer with Aerosil.
ΔH_{BP}	Heat of fusion in J/g of bound polymer.
G_c^*	Complex shear modulus of composite.
G_c'	Storage modulus of composite.
G_c''	Loss modulus of composite.
$tg \delta$	G''/G'
G_f^*, G_l^*, G_m^*	Complex shear modulus of filler, interphase and matrix.
φ_f, φ_l	Volume fraction of filler and interphase.
ν_f, ν_l, ν_m	Poisson ratio of filler, interphase and matrix.

INTRODUCTION

The properties of filled polymers are mainly determined by volume fractions, the shape of the filler particles and bulk properties of the components, but they can also be influenced by specific surface interactions between fillers and polymers (1, 2, 3). Direct evidence of the interaction of polymers and fillers is given by the occurrence of 'bound' polymer (3, 4, 5, 6). Bound polymer is the portion of a polymer in a composite which cannot be extracted with solvent, although the polymer as such (without filler) is quickly and completely dissolved by the solvent used.

In comparison with the work done on filled elastomers, relatively few investigations are known which deal with bound polymer in filled thermoplastics, but recently several authors have demonstrated the presence of bound polymer in various polyethylene-filler composites (7, 8, 9).

In the composite model we used, all particles are surrounded by a bound polymer shell and are well dispersed in the matrix material.

The interphase in the composites is identical with the bound polymer layer as the properties of the bound polymer layer are distinguishable from the bulk matrix properties.

The objective of the work, part of which is reported here, was to analyse in more depth the structure and properties of the interphase in silicate polyethylene systems and to gain more insight into the influence of specific interphase properties on overall composite properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

On a two-roll mill, composites of high-density polyethylene (Stamylan 9309, $\rho_{23} = 963 \text{ kg/m}^3$, MFI = 8 g/10 min) and silicas (Degussa Aerosil OX50, 130 and 200 with BET surfaces 50, 130 and 200 m^2/g , $\rho_f = 2200 \text{ kg/m}^3$) were blended for 15 minutes at 443 K. The resulting sheets were pressed to a thickness of 0.1 cm and cooled from 443 K to room temperature at a rate of 40 K/min. The bound polymer was determined by extraction of small samples 1 cm x 1 cm x 0.1 cm in agitated xylene at 398 K. The dissolving procedure lasted 4 hours fresh solvent being supplied every hour. Within the temperature range of 393-408 K no influence was found of the dissolving temperature on the amount of bound polymer; even when another solvent was used (dekaline) in the temperature range of 393-423 K, the same results were obtained. Afterwards, the samples were dried for 24 hours in a furnace at 353 K. The ash content of the composite samples and of the residual fractions after extraction was determined by a standard thermogravimetric method (Perkin Elmer TGS-2).

Composites pressed to a thickness of $\approx 100 \mu\text{m}$ at 443 K and residual filler particles with bound polymer were treated with hydrofluoric acid for 10 hours at room temperature until the ash content was lower than 0.5 %. In this way the total polymer in the composites as well as the bound polymer could be isolated. Gel Permeation Chromatography was performed with a Waters GPC-2000 with 6000S-3000S Toya Soda columns in 1, 2, 4-trichlorobenzene at 403 K. The heat of fusion ΔH in J/g was determined from the second heating curve on a Perkin Elmer DSC-2 (heating and cooling rate 5 K/min). Dynamic-mechanical characteristics were measured with a compensated DSM-torsion pendulum at a constant frequency of 0.2153 c/s and a constant amplitude.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thickness and molecular mass distribution of the interphase

The results of the extraction procedure with xylene are presented in Fig. 1 for several composites. BP is defined as the volume of bound insoluble polymer divided by the volume of polymer in the composite.

For gelfree polymers, Pliskin and Tokita (10) have derived the expression

$$BP = \Delta R \frac{\varphi_f \rho_f A_f}{1 - \varphi_f} \quad (1)$$

where ΔR is the average thickness of the bound polymer layer, in m, φ_f is the volume fraction, ρ_f the density in kg/m^3 , A_f the specific surface area of the filler particles in m^2/kg .

Fig. 1. Pliskin-Tokita plot for several Aerosil-HDPE composites.

It can be concluded from Fig. 1 that the average thickness of the bound polymer layer is 3.6 nm. This value is comparable with the values of 2–8 nm found for several carbon-black-filled rubbers (10) and higher than the value of 2 nm found by Kendall (8) for several silicate-filled polyethylenes. An explanation of these differences may be that the amount of bound polymer depends on the surface activity of the fillers as well as on the molecular mass distribution of the polymer.

A more detailed theory which takes into account these facts was developed by Meissner (11). This theory treats the phenomenon of bound polymer as random adsorption of structural units of polymer onto reactive sites which are assumed to exist on the surface of the filler particles. Only one adjustable parameter is needed, the filler surface per reactive site A_0 , to calculate the amounts and the molecular mass distributions of the unbound polymer and the bound polymer.

$$U = \int_0^{\infty} w(y) e^{-qy} dy \quad (2)$$

$$BP = 1 - U \quad (3)$$

The molecular mass distributions are given by

$$U \cdot w_U(y) dy = w(y) e^{-qy} dy \quad (4)$$

and

$$BP \cdot w_{BP}(y) dy = w(y) dy - w(y) e^{-qy} dy \quad (5)$$

The theoretical amount of bound polymer is calculated for $A_0 = 18.4 \text{ nm}^2$ and shown in Fig. 1, based on the molecular mass distribution of polyethylene in the composites. A typical example of the molecular mass distributions for bound and unbound polymer, calculated with formulas (4) and (5), are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Molecular mass distributions of the total polymer w , the unbound polymer $U \cdot w_U$ and the bound polymer $BP \cdot w_{BP}$, compared with Meissner's theory for a 20 vol. % Al30-HDPE composite with $BP = 0.24$.

The same surface area of filler per single reactive site A_0 could be used to calculate the molecular characteristics of the composite with 20 vol. % A200. As shown in Fig. 1 the amount of bound polymer for the composite with 20 vol. % A50 predicted by Meissner is too high. A good fit was found with $A_0 = 32.6 \text{ nm}^2$, both for the amount of bound polymer and for the molecular mass distributions of bound and unbound polymer.

Thermal properties

The heat of fusion of the bound polymer ΔH_{BP} was determined by means of differential scanning calorimetry of the total undissolved fractions and the ash contents of these fractions.

$$\Delta H_{BP} + \text{Aerosil} = \Delta H_{BP} \frac{\text{wt. bound polymer}}{\text{wt. bound polymer} + \text{wt. Aerosil}} \quad (6)$$

The slope of the straight line in Fig. 3 represents the heat of fusion of the bound polymer ΔH_{BP} . The value found is 110 J/g, a low value in comparison with the value found for the unfilled polymer (225 J/g). The value of 110 J/g approximately equals the value we found for the bound polymer in kaolin-polyethylene composites (9). The low value of the heat of fusion and the decreased crystallization and melting temperatures indicate that the crystallization process is hindered by the adsorption of the polymer onto the filler surface. In agreement with these results, the total heat of fusion in the composites is changed by the amount of bound polymer present (12).

Fig. 3. Heat of fusion of the undissolved fraction after extraction with xylene as a function of the weight fraction of polymer in the undissolved fraction.

Dynamic-mechanical properties

The dynamic-mechanical properties of the bound polymer in the presence of the filler particles were measured on a pressed sample after extraction with xylene. To calculate the properties of the bound polymer alone, a correction for the presence of the particles and vacuoles was made by using a dynamic-mechanical composite model. The model used was an extension of the van der Poel method (13) and allowed the calculation of complex dynamic-mechanical properties of composites with particulate fillers with and without an interphase (14).

$$G_c^* = G_c' + i G_c'' = G_c^* (G_f^*, G_1^*, G_m^*, \phi_f, \phi_1, \nu_f, \nu_1, \nu_m) \quad (7)$$

Fig. 4. Dynamic-mechanical shear properties as a function of temperature for HDPE and the interphase.

In Fig. 4, the results for the calculated bound polymer properties are compared with the dynamic-mechanical properties of the unfilled HDPE sample. The bound polymer shows two aspects (1), at lower temperatures, the behaviour resembles that of a disturbed polyethylene such as for example a chlorinated polyethylene (2) at higher temperatures the bound polymer has characteristics of a cross-linked polymer. Both aspects are compatible with the view of partially bound polymer molecules at the filler surface with hindered molecular mobility. Using the theoretical model to calculate the complex properties of the composites with interphase from the properties of their constituents it was possible to predict composite properties over a wide temperature range (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Dynamic-mechanical shear properties as a function of temperature for 20 vol % A130 in HDPE compared with theoretical calculations.

CONCLUSIONS

(1) The thickness of the bound polymer layer or interphase in Aerosil-HDPE composites was found to be 3.6 nm. The molecular mass distribution of bound and unbound polymer could be described by Meissner's theory.

(2) The heat of fusion ΔH_{HP} was found to be 110 J/g, a value appreciably lower than the 225 J/g found for the unfilled polymer.

(3) The dynamic-mechanical properties of the bound-polymer are different from the properties of the unfilled polymer and permit, with the help of a model, the calculation of the dynamic-mechanical properties of Aerosil-HDPE composites in a wide temperature range.

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